

Original Research Report

Strategies for Enhancing Home Economics Teachers' Service Delivery in Some Selected Public Secondary Schools in Lagos State

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Abstract: This study determined the strategies for enhancing home economics teachers' service delivery in some selected public secondary schools in Yaba, Lagos State. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Population for the study was 150 and the sample size was 50. Purposive sampling technique was adopted. Structured questionnaires were the instrument used for data collection. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Findings revealed that some of the factors that have negative impacts on Home Economics teachers service delivery are obsolete curriculum that are not in tune with current realities, lack of meaningful job schedule, lack of proper planning and provision of needed technological tools, facilities and equipment needed foreffective teaching and learning of home economics, lack of proper procedures for measuring the growth of each individual teacher and student performance, inability to make result driven evaluation that would help teachers appreciate their roles as home economist and lack of clear understanding of the subject matter. It was concluded that that employees provides favorable and satisfying working conditions, teachers should be an embodiment of a constant search for updated knowledge in their various fields. Amongst the recommendations made were that there should be training and re-training for teachers, increased remuneration so as to enhance their service delivery and only professionally trained Home Economist should be allowed to teach Home Economics as a subject.

Keywords: Delivery, Enhancing, Service, Strategies, Teachers'

1. Introduction

Home economics is one of the vocational subjects taught at junior secondary schools in Nigeria and it is a compulsory part of the curriculum in the secondary schools. It is taught as an integral core subject, which comprises food and nutrition, clothing and textile and home management. The importance of exposing learners to home economics curriculum is for individual and societal development and it has been widely acknowledged and revealed that the knowledge and skills gained from home economics makes a considerable contribution to young people's personal and social development. Mbah, Orhewere and Osifeso, (2019).

Strategies on the other hand are plan of action designed to achieve a long term aim. Actions that managers take to attain one or more of their organizational goals are regarded as strategies and it results from the detailed intended or pattern of activities as organization adapts to its environment or competes with it. A functional strategy is always concerned with development and efficiency, (Isyanovan, 2023). In other to improve home economics curricular, the programme is constantly being subjected to change to meet up with the dynamic society. As it were, the world is constantly changing and individuals, families and communities are daily confronted with scientific challenges capable of affecting what should be the content of home economics education for societal advancement. Prior to this era, home economics education programme was to equip the individual with competencies to maintain family life. Currently the program is being faced with challenges for survival, inability to sustain relevance in the dynamic economy. Maduagu and Ogbonna (2023) noted that home economics graduates who in turn are teachers of this subjects also seem not to be well equipped with relevant practical skills needed for the enablement of transfer of knowledge to students.

A teacher is a person who delivers an educational program, assesses student's participation in a structured set of activities designed to help them learn, develop skills, knowledge and required attitudes. The quality and extent of learners' achievement are determined primarily by teacher competence, sensitivity and teacher motivation. A classroom teacher is expected to provide learning experiences through the process of curriculum implementation. Mbah et al. (2019). Teachers are very important in educational capability of producing desired learning outcomes. How they impart knowledge, act and interact with students in the classroom are more necessary than the teaching, Maduagu and Ogbonna (2023). Teachers have numerous roles to play in the process of teaching and learning, most especially in teaching of Home Economics as subject. Home Economics teachers need to be competent in his/her area of specialization and be able to apply different methods of teaching strategies. Most students in the junior secondary school are of the opinion that Home Economics is not important and relevant because they feel that the skills they acquired during their secondary school programme cannot sustain them economically after school and they seem not to see Home Economic as a subject they can exploit and be empowered economically. It is therefore important to encourage teachers so as to further improve on their service delivery.

Service delivery on the other hand is a business framework that supplies services from a provider to a client and it is very critical for any organisational success. Enhanced service delivery initiatives focus on continuous performance improvement in an organisation. To ensure that the service package

and service encounter fit the needs of the students, schools must focus on proactive measures to design and deliver their service concept especially in public secondary school. Masara (2017) noted that service delivery is valuable in organisations because it improves or enhances service operation which in this context means teaching and learning of home economics in public junior secondary schools

Public junior secondary school is a school for intermediate between elementary school and college usually basic 7-9. It a school that provides a three year post primary course of full time instruction suitable for pupils between ages twelve and fifteen years. Schools that are maintained at public expense for educating of children of a particular community or district are known as public schools. They constitute a part of a system of free education, Bashar (2020). A teacher who teach in public secondary schools needs to be encouraged by way of increase in salaries, timely promotion, payment of allowances, training and also retraining of teachers to enhance efficiency and relevance.

This study responds to sustainable development goal four which has to do with ensuring inclusive and quality education as well as promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. The findings of this study have implications for Home Economic teachers because there is an urgent need for them to ensure the acquisition of relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship. There are several studies on teaching home economics but none reviewed by the authors focused on strategies for enhancing home economics teachers' service delivery. This study filled this gap in literature.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Education is the foundation of National, socio-economic and political development. The quality of citizens' level of education would determine the level of its national progress. Nigerian education is plagued with multidimensional problems, ranging from poor funding, misappropriation of allocated funds, dilapidated and inadequate infrastructure, none functional curricular and obsolete instructional methods. A nation like Nigeria does not have histories of heavy investment in education. There is the challenge of incessant strikes by teaching and non-teaching personnel in all the three tiers of education. This may perhaps not be unconnected with generalized poor working conditions and the ongoing brain drain of our best human resources since the 1980s to date. Necessary skills gained through home economics make a considerable contribution to young people's personal and social development and as well prepares them for the world of works in a wide range of area. Hence the need to examine strategies for Enhancing Home Economics Teachers' Service Delivery in Some Selected Public Junior Secondary Schools in Lagos State with the view of making recommendations that will better improve the subject for the present and future generations

1.2. Purpose of the Review

The general purpose of this review article is to determine the Strategies for Enhancing Home Economics Teachers' Service Delivery. Specific purposes is to:

- (a) Identify the impact of occupational roles on Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery
- (b) Examine problems associated with Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery

(c) Identify coping strategies for enhancing Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery

1.3. Review Questions

The following review questions guided the study:

- (a) What are the impact of occupational roles on Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery?
- (b) What are the problems associated with Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery?
- (c) What are the coping strategies for enhancing Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery?

1.4. Theoretical Framework

Theoretical framework of a study is the blueprint underpinning the research one is embarking on. Adelana, Ayanwale, Ishola, Oladejo and Adewuyi (2023). This study was anchored on transformative learning theory which was propounded by Jack Mezirow in the year 1978 as cited by Bashar (2020). This theory suggest that everyone learns differently and understanding the different ways that humans learns is crucial to educational success and by understanding how learning happens, educators can maximize their efforts and create classrooms' where learners can thrive. This theory is related to this study because the study examined problems associated with Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery as well as coping strategies for enhancing Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

This study adopted a descriptive research design. Thus, the researcher sees it necessary to use this design because she wants to investigate and determine the Strategies for Enhancing Home Economics Teachers' Service Delivery In some selected public Junior Secondary Schools.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

Approval was sought from Department of Home Economics, Lagos State University of Education, Ijanikin and Lagos State District IV before conducting the study amongst the Home Economics undergraduates and Junior Secondary School students. Also, informed consent was obtained from Home Economics Teachers before participating in the study. Ethic of privacy and confidentiality of all participants was ensured in accordance with Home Economics Research Association of Nigerian (HERAN) research ethics.

2.2. Area of the study:

The study was carried out in Yaba Local Government Area in Lagos State. The reason for choosing Lagos State is because there are many students offering Home Economics at Junior Secondary School level in Lagos State.

2.3 Population and sample

Population consist of a total of one hundred and fifty (150) which comprised of fifty (50) Home Economics Undergraduates Students, forty (40) Home Economics Teachers (Source: Human Resource Office) and (60) sixty Junior Secondary School Students (Source: Admission Office 2021/22). There

was no sampling since the population was a manageable size. Hence, the entire population of one hundred and fifty were used for the study

2.4 Instrument for data Collection and study procedure

A Structured Questionnaire on Strategies for Enhancing Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery in Public Junior Secondary School (SEHJSC) was used for data collection. Page | 67

2.5 Data Collection Technique

Data for the study were collected by the researcher with the aid of a research assistant. This assistant was briefed on the purpose and nature of the study, how to distribute and collect copies of the questionnaire

2.6 Data Analysis Technique

Data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation. To achieve this, SPSS version 25 was used to analyse the data and it was accepted at 0.05 level of significance.

3. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on the Impact of occupational role on Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery

S/N	Impact of occupational role on Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Lack of meaningful job schedule may have a negative impact on Home Economics teachers.	4.00	0.00	Agreed
2	Lack of adequate provision of adequate ICT facilities for Home Economics programmes.	3.86	0.43	Agreed
3	Obsolete curriculum that is not in tune with current realities.	3.70	0.75	Agreed
4	Lack of Proper planning and provision of needed technological tools, facilities and equipment needed for effective teaching and learning of Home Economics.	3.60	0.77	Agreed
5	Lack of proper procedures for measuring the growth of each individual teacher and student performance	3.73	0.49	Agreed
6	Inability to make result driven evaluation that will help to teachers appreciate their roles as home economics teachers.	3.50	0.86	Agreed
7	Role overload due to too many roles and demands on Home Economics teachers.	3.40	0.89	Disagreed
8.	General mental ability of a teacher will affect his or her performance	3.36	0.77	Disagreed
9.	Clear understanding of the subject matter will affect teachers performance positively	3.62	0.94	Agreed
10.	Unconducive environment will affect teachers performance positively	3.33	0.47	Disagreed

Key: Number = 50 respondents, \bar{x} =Mean, SD= Standard Deviation.

3.1. Table 1: Ten (10) items were used to elicit responses on 4-point Likert scale of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Results from the table showed that three of the items from the table above were disagreed upon while seven items on the highlighted items on the Impact of occupational role on Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery were strongly agreed upon. The items agreed upon included lack of adequate provision of ICT facilities for home economics programmes. Obsolete curriculum that is not in tune with current realities of meaningful job schedule may have a negative impact on home economics teachers, lack of proper planning and provision of needed technological tools, facilities and equipment needed for effective teaching and learning of home economics, lack of proper procedures for measuring the growth of each individual teacher and student performance, inability to make result driven evaluation that will help to teachers appreciate their roles as home economics teachers and clear understanding of the subject matter will affect teachers performance positively while the items disagreed upon as the impact of occupational role on home economics Teachers Service Delivery included that role overload due to too many roles and demands on Home Economics teachers, general mental ability of a teacher will affect his or performance and unconducive environment will affect teachers performance positively. Also, Standard deviation responses ranged from 0.00 to 0.94 implying that the mean responses on the Impact of occupational role on Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery were not far from each other.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on the problems associated with Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery?

S/N	Problems associated with Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Not presenting learning objectives through qualified Home Economics teachers.	3.83	0.46	Agreed
2	Not facilitating students' awareness on the expected learning outcomes.	1,26	0.44	Disagreed
3	Not giving learners feedback on exercises and activities carried out on-line.	3.62	0.71	Agreed
4	Teachers do not help students to link up previous learning objectives with current materials to be learned.	1.23	0.67	Disagreed
5	Not guiding, structuring and offering adequate guidance during teaching and learning.	2..03	0.66	Disagreed

6	Not promoting of personal relationship between the learners and teacher through well-developed online communication tools.	3.70	0.46	Agreed
7	Not helping learners find their way in and around the subject matter by repeating sections where appropriate.	3.80	0.66	Agreed
8	Not providing clear instructions on what students should be able to do on completion of the material in terms of objectives.	3.67	0.92	Agreed
9	Not engage them in exercises and activities that cause them to work with the subject matter, rather than merely reading about it.	2.97	1.15	Agreed
10	Not giving students the liberty to judge for themselves whether they are learning successfully.	2.03	0.66	Disagreed

Key: Number = 50 respondents, \bar{x} =Mean, SD= Standard Deviation.

3.2. Table 2: Ten (10) items were used to elicit responses on 4-point scale of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Result from the table showed that four of the items highlighted as the problems associated with Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery were strongly disagreed upon while six of the items were agreed upon. The items strongly agreed on included not presenting learning objectives through qualified Home Economics teachers, not giving learners feedback on exercises and activities carried out on-line, not promoting of personal relationship between the learners and teacher through well-developed online communication tools, not helping learners find their way in and around the subject matter by repeating sections where appropriate, not providing clear instructions on what students should be able to do on completion of the material in terms of objectives and not engage them in exercises and activities that cause them to work with the subject matter, rather than merely reading about it while the items disagreed upon are that teachers do not help students to link up previous learning objectives with current materials to be learned, teachers do not help students to link up previous learning objectives with current materials to be learned, not guiding, structuring and offering adequate guidance during teaching and learning and not giving students the liberty to judge for themselves whether they are learning successfully. Standard deviation responses ranged from 0.15 to 0.71 implying that the mean responses on the Impact of occupational role on Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery were not far from each other.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation responses on the coping strategies for enhancing Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery.

S/N	Coping strategies for enhancing Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Arousing attention and retention by presenting learning objectives through qualified teachers.	1.06	0.25	Disagreed
2	Facilitating students' awareness on the expected learning outcomes.	1.20	0.48	Disagreed
3	Giving learners feedback on exercises and activities carried out in class.	3.76	0.67	Agreed
4	Helping students to link up previous learning objectives with current materials to be learned.	3.80	0.40	Agreed
5	Guiding, structuring and offering adequate guidance during teaching and learning.	3.56	0.62	Agreed
6	Promoting of personal relationship between the students and the teacher through well-developed communication channel.	1.40	0.77	Disagreed
7	Helping learners understand the subject matter by repeating sections where appropriate.	3.66	0.81	Agreed
8	Telling students what they need to do in other to be able to tackle the instructional materials in principles and practices.	1.30	0.83	Disagreed
9	Providing clear instructions on what students should be able to do on completion of the material in terms of objectives.	1.36	0.71	Disagreed
10	Teaching from concrete to abstract	1.97	0.67	Disagreed
11	Engaging students in exercises and activities that helps them to work with the subject matter, rather than merely reading about it.	1.46	0.93	Disagreed
12	Giving students the liberty to evaluate themselves	1.40	0.89	Disagreed

Key: Number = 50 respondents, \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation.

3.3. Table 3: Twelve (12) items were used to elicit responses on 4-point scale of strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Result from the table showed that majority of the highlighted items on coping strategies for enhancing Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery were strongly disagreed upon while few were agreed upon. Eight of the items were disagreed upon from the table above and four of the items were agreed upon. The items disagreed on included that

Arousing attention and retention by presenting learning objectives through qualified teachers, facilitating students' awareness on the expected learning outcomes, promoting of personal relationship between the students and the teacher through well-developed communication channel, telling students what they need to do in other to be able to tackle the instructional materials in principles and practices,

providing clear instructions on what students should be able to do on completion of the material in terms of objectives, teaching from concrete to abstract, engaging students in exercises and activities that helps them to work with the subject matter, rather than merely reading about it., giving students the liberty to evaluate themselves while the items agreed upon included, giving learners feedback on exercises and activities carried out in class, helping students to link up previous learning objectives with current materials to be learned, guiding, structuring and offering adequate guidance during teaching and learning and helping learners understand the subject matter by repeating sections where appropriate. Standard deviation responses ranged from 0.25 to 0.93 implying that the mean responses on the Impact coping strategies for enhancing Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery were not far from each other. Page | 71

3.4. Description/discussion

Findings revealed that some of the factors that have negative impacts on occupational roles are lack of adequate provision of ICT facilities for home economics programmes, obsolete curriculum that is not in tune with current realities of meaningful job schedule, lack of proper planning and provision of needed technological tools, facilities and equipment needed for effective teaching and learning of home economics, lack of proper procedures for measuring the growth of each individual teacher and student performance, inability to make result driven evaluation that will help to teachers appreciate their roles as home economics teachers and clear understanding of the subject matter will affect teachers performance positively. These are in line with the assertion of (Dislere et al., 2020) which stated that teaching is one of the oldest professions, the workload of teachers are influenced by several factors including the more formal and difficult procedures in doing their work, making them find enough time in planning their work. In addition, teachers are not just responsible for improving students' knowledge but also responsible for social and emotional development of their students, thus increasing the responsibility of the teaching profession. Masara (2017) noted that to achieve this status teachers and most thinkers and philosophers of the past who are still remembered because they had organizational success were able to achieve that by having satisfied, motivated employees and good leadership. Therefore, a good leadership style is required to lead teachers and to enhance the efficiency of home economics teachers in terms of service delivery. This implies that positive impact of occupational role on Home Economics teachers will enhance Teachers Service Delivery

Findings also revealed that some of problems associated with Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery are not presenting learning objectives through qualified Home Economics teachers, not giving learners feedback on exercises and activities carried out on-line, not promoting of personal relationship between the learners and teacher through well-developed online communication tools. not helping learners find their way in and around the subject matter by repeating sections where appropriate, not providing clear instructions on what students should be able to do on completion of the material in terms of objectives and not engaging them in exercises and activities that causes them to work with the subject matter, rather than merely reading about it. This findings corroborates with Dislere et al. (2020) who stated that in all organization and establishments; that employees put in their

best when working conditions are favourable and satisfying. Teaching as a profession has lost many teachers to other professions due to poor remunerations; many teachers have migrated and are still migrating to other professions. In Colleges of Education especially when a teacher is not satisfied, performance will be low, and low performance affects both the students and the reputation of the institution. Poor academic performance of students in Nigeria has been linked to poor teacher's performance in terms of accomplishing the teaching task, negative attitude to work and poor teaching habits which have been attributed to poor motivation. It has also been observed that conditions that would make for effective teaching such as resources available to teachers, general conditions of infrastructure as well as instructional materials in Public Secondary Schools in Nigeria are poor. These prevailing conditions would definitely constitute a negative influence on instructional quality of public school, which may translate to poor academic performance, attitudes and values of secondary school students.

Findings indicated that coping strategies for enhancing Home Economics Teachers Service Delivery are rousing attention and retention by presenting learning objectives through qualified teachers. Facilitating students' awareness on the expected learning outcomes, promoting of personal relationship between the students and the teacher through well-developed communication channel, telling students what they need to do in other to be able to tackle the instructional materials in principles and practices, providing clear instructions on what students should be able to do on completion of the material in terms of objectives, teaching from concrete to abstract, engaging students in exercises and activities that helps them to work with the subject matter, rather than merely reading about and giving students the liberty to evaluate themselves. This is in line with the assertions of Azonuche (2020) who stated some coping strategies as using time plan, preparing properly for a given task and planning to do related jobs at a time to avoid confusion. (Dislere et al., 2020) mentioned that setting priorities do the most important things first, avoiding procrastination (delaying activities), being prepared to accept other challenges internal/ external, discussing challenges with colleagues or seeking advice from superiors, looking for role models within the system to guide one, not dwelling too much on the challenge and looking ahead to overcome challenges. The study was limited to home economics undergraduates, junior secondary students and teachers as a result of time factor. Getting students willing to participate in the study is also a major limitation. The suggestions for further study includes the determination of motivational factors for enhancing classroom management among home economics teachers and lecturers in some selected senior secondary schools as well as in tertiary institutions.

4. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that in every profession and in almost all organization and establishments, that employees put in their best when working conditions are favorable and satisfying. Teaching as a versatile field requires at all times the correct identification of indices of developments in the society. This responsibility makes it imperative that teachers should be an embodiment of a constant search for updated knowledge in various their fields. Some of the coping

strategies identified were using time plan, preparing properly for a given task and setting priorities to do the most important things first, avoiding procrastination, being prepared to accept other challenges, discussing challenges with colleagues or seeking advice from superiors, looking for role models within the system to guide one and not dwelling too much on the challenges encountered while trying to carry out ones day to day activities as a teacher. Among the actionable recommendations made were that policy makers and educational administrators should constantly review home economics curriculum to be in tune with the current realities and implementing strategies targeted training and re-training program for home economics teachers should be strictly encouraged.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: KPO

Formal analysis: KPO and UGO

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Methodology: KPO and TFO

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Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article: further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author

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